

Development of Shotokan Karate, a chronology by Karate Coach Dr. Pradeep Kumar Yadav

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In 1930, Funakoshi further expanded Karate studies in Japan. The colleges were the significant destinations of Karate study, and they were impacted by research on physiology and workout. Under Yoshitaka, the improvement of Shotokan Karate truly quickened that brought straightforwardness in the intensity of punching and kicking methods. This learning consolidated into the Kihon (basics) of Shotokan Karate. During the 1930s, Karate's further styles, Goju-Ryu, Shito-Ryu, and Wado-Ryu, had been created notwithstanding the form of Shotokan Karate. These styles were additionally presented by Masters from Okinawa, which are as follows:

1. **Shito-Ryu (Japan)**, which was established by Master Kenwa Mabuni in 1928, and was based on practicing a lot of Kata to bring out perfection instances.
2. **Goju-Ryu (Okinawa)**, which was formed by Master Chojun Miyagi in 1930, and was based on using circular block and Jujitsu techniques.
3. **Shoto-Ryu (Japan)**, which was defined by Master Gichin Funakoshi in 1938, and was based on doing wide stances that deliver powerful attacks rapidly on an opponent.
4. **Wado-Ryu (Japan)**, which was created by Master Hironori Otsuka in 1939, and was based on a natural posture to dodge the assailant's attack or to make it minimize.

On January 29, 1936, the first official Shotokan Dojo "Dai-Nihon Karate- do Shoto-Kan" was opened in Zoshigaya, Mejiro, Tokyo. Japanese Karate-ka contributed funds to manufacture the main building of Karate dojo, which they named Shotokan in regard of Funakoshi Sensei. Unfortunately, it was demolished by an allied forces' air attack on April 29, 1945. Under Master Funakoshi, the first Shihans (Senior teachers) were **Takeshi Shimoda** (1901-1934), Master's first remarkable student, who died in 1934 at a young age and **Yoshitaka Funakoshi** (1906-1945) who died young in 1945. The number of individuals wishing to start practice was increasing day by day. The Katas modified to adjust to a dynamic new style. After being seen by the Japanese Ministry of Education during a Karate exhibit, Funakoshi approached it to carry his Karate to colleges in Japan for guidance. His presentation of the Karate technique was successful there and he sent forward an assortment of extraordinary students, like Takagi and Nakayama of Nippon Karate Kyokai, **Yoshida** of Takudai, **Obata** of Keio, **Noguchi** of Waseda, and Otsuka, the organizer of Wado-Ryu karate to different colleges and universities in some territories of Japan.

After the 2nd World War residue settled **in 1945**, one of Master Funakoshi's top students, Masatoshi Nakayama started to sort out the rest of the students and recoup the lost preparing strategies of Kata and Kumite. Gichin Funakoshi assumed a significant job in acquainting Japan with karate from Okinawa, acclimated to decrease injury and converged with approaches for athletic preparation. There were some senior students of Master Funakoshi including **Masatoshi Nakayama**, **Isao Obata**, and **Hidetaka Nishiyama** who wanted to form an organization which would be dedicated to the promotion, education, management and research of Karate. Therefore, on **May 27, 1949** an organization was formed which is known as **Nihon Karate Kyokai or Japan Karate Association (JKA)**. This organization was totally dedicated to Master Funakoshi's endeavors. Master Funakoshi was appointed as the supreme commander of the JKA and Hidetaka Nishiyama was appointed as the Chief Instructor. The Japan Karate Association (JKA) started framing rules for Karate challenges, including a focus on Kata and Kumite. These rivalries aligned Karate closer with different indigenous Japanese hand-to-hand fights, for example, kendo and judo. Today, Karate-do is spread over several nations around the globe. He needed to clarify that the essential tutoring and preparation must be the significant prime point. At this point, Master Funakoshi had, for quite some time, been instructing Karate to secondary school and college students. Subsequently, Karate clubs had jumped up at advanced education foundations all over Japan, which is another motivation behind why Karate has moved towards being regarded as it is today.

In May 1949, a few of the first Shotokan Karate Masters split from the JKA association. One of these was **Hirokazu Kanazawa** (May 3, 1931 – December 8, 2019, known as "**Kancho**." Kanazawa was the protege of the late superintendent of the Shotokan style, Masatoshi Nakayama, and was one of the only a handful few outstanding Karate experts who contemplated under Master Gichin Funakoshi himself.

On April 10, 1957, the Ministry of Education, Japan, gave legal recognition to the JKA, turning it into a rightful institute. After sixteen days past this recognition, Master Funakoshi passed away on **April 26, 1957** at the age of 89. An enormous open remembrance was held at the Ryogoku Kokugikan (Ryogoku National Sumo Hall) which included 20,000 individuals, including numerous sports celebrities and government officials that came to offer their tribute. A commemoration landmark to Master Funakoshi was built up at **Engakuji Temple in**

Kamakura, Japan. On April 29, every year, the date of the Shoto Festival, individuals from the JKA pay a privileged visit to this memorial. A commemoration to Gichin Funakoshi was raised by the Shotokai at Engakuji, a monastery in Kamakura, on December 1, 1968. Designed by **Kenji Ogata** the landmark highlights calligraphy by Funakoshi and **Sogen Asahina** (1891–1979, the main priest of the monastery which bears the words "**Karate ni sente nashi,**" which means "**There is no first attack in Karate.**"

GRANDMASTER GICHIN FUNAKOSHI MEMORIAL AT ENGAKUJI TEMPLE, KAMAKURA, JAPAN. (The aforesaid photograph has been taken from www.deviantart.com and is being used as part of fair use. The copyrights and other intellectual rights of the said photograph belong to the respective right owners.

The JKA had already started its well-known educator training project and started to create the absolute, most capable, gifted, and formidable Karate specialists on the planet. Ace Nakayama utilized the educator course to spread the humble Okinawan Karate worldwide. Remarkable educators from the JKA instructional classes included Masters **Hidetaka Nishiyama** (October 10, 1928 – November 7, 2008), **Teruyuki Okazaki** (June 22, 1931 – April 21, 2020), **Yutaka Yaguchi** (November 14, 1932), **Hirokazu Kanazawa** (May 3, 1931 – December 8, 2019), **Keinosuke Enoda** (July 4, 1935 – March 29, 2003), **Takayuki Mikami** (January 1, 1933), **Tetsuhiko Asai** (June 7, 1935 – August 15, 2006), and numerous others. These incredible educators formed the universe of Karate work during the height of its ubiquity during the 1960s and 1970s.

During the 1st Japanese Master's Championship in 1957, as indicated in the reports by the JKA Instructor **Teruyuki Okazaki**, he was providing guidance in the Central Dojo of the JKA consistently, straight up to a couple of days before his death. The JKA proceeded with the spreading of Shotokan Karate with Funakoshi's point, with overall accomplishment under the initiative of **Masatoshi Nakayama**. Nakayama set down the required measures for the procedures, groupings, and use of the Shotokan Kata in his books, which are followed till now.

ENGAKUJI TEMPLE, KAMAKURA, JAPAN. (Photo by Andrea Schaffer from Sydney, Australia. The aforesaid photograph has been taken from www.commons.wikimedia.org and is being used as part of fair use. The copyrights and other intellectual rights of the said photograph belong to the respective right owners.)

The 1st JKA All Japan Karate Championship was held in **October 1957** in Tokyo. When this yearly competition's framework was setting up, it wasn't long before there were many JKA karate branches in towns, schools, and renowned colleges in Japan. **In 1958**, Master Nakayama was delegated as the Chief Instructor. **In 1961**, His Majesty, the Crown Prince of Japan (presently His Majesty the Emperor of Japan), went to attend the fifth JKA All Japan Karate Championship. The JKA karate had become noticeable. This period saw dynamic advancement in the art of Karate. As a consequence of consistent coaching among educators, the complete framework of Karate was formed. For the first time, the best forms for each Kumite position, stance, and action merged in a proper scientific way. There was a clear distinction between the "correct" and "incorrect" approach to execute every technique, position, punch, and kick. When these methods were created, several teachers went abroad to spread Karate's specialty around the globe. The JKA was the principal karate association to set up dojo outside Japan. That's why the JKA is so famous and influential in the world. During this period, the JKA further built up its karate guidance framework and keeping in mind the incredible growth of its branch dojo all through Japan, it started sending some of its most exceptionally trained, proficient educators to America, Europe, and the Middle East to instruct and build up the dojo. Karate was turning into success outside Japan as well. Moreover, the JKA turned into the leading karate association to send its certified full-time educators to demonstrate Karate in colleges. Ace Teruyuki Okazaki and Hidetaka Nishiyama (October 10, 1928 – November 7, 2008), were instructed by the JKA in 1961, to spread Shotokan Karate in the USA.

In 1975, by acknowledging Karate's entry into the Olympics as a top priority, the first universal competition supported by the JKA, the IAKF (International Amateur Karate Federation) World Cup was held in the U.S., and it continued for the three more times later also. Notwithstanding, to safeguard the whole system and soul of Ippon Shobu (bringing down the adversary with one blow), the JKA organized another competition, the first-ever worldwide Shoto World Cup Karate Championship Tournament in 1985 and that was a declaration of how much global a martial technique Karate had become.

In 1977, Ace Okazaki built up the "**International Shotokan Karate Federation**" (ISKF) in Philadelphia which was assigned the overall central command. The ISKF ceaselessly developed and thrived as a part of the Japan Karate Association (JKA until 2007), setting up an Instructor Training Institute in the USA to reflect the

JKA training program.

In 1978, Hirokazu Kanazawa (1931–2019), 10th Dan, split away from the JKA and formed **Shotokan Karate-do International Federation (SKIF)**. Kanazawa had trained under Masatoshi Nakayama and Hidetaka Nishiyama who were the two students of legend Gichin Funakoshi. SKIF presented components of TAI-CHI, especially in the matter of balance, and effectively advanced the development of Shotokan art. Kanazawa is viewed as one of the most splendid Shotokan master. Most prominently, he won the kumite title at the main JKA Open Tournament (in 1957 with a wrecked hand). Kanazawa was granted 10th Dan in 2000. Established in **October, 1978** with over two million individuals in 103 nations around the world, the SKIF is the world's most prominent Shotokan Karate association. Shotokan Karate is one of the most prevalent of the present-day styles. It is the most dominant and dynamic of Japanese techniques. In his late 70's, Master Hirokazu Kanazawa was the Chairman and Chief Instructor of the Shotokan Karate-do International Federation (SKIF) and was holding the evaluation of 10th DAN.

Master Masatoshi Nakayama (April 13, 1913 – April 15, 1987), who became the second Chief Instructor of the JKA after Sensei Funakoshi died in November 1957, was the only man to spread Karate worldwide in the **1960s and 1970s** and put it on a scientific method through Kinesiology, Anatomy, Psychology, and Physics associated with Karate techniques. He had started learning Karate under the incredible ace Gichin Funakoshi in 1931. After moving on from Takushoko University in 1937, he had gone to Peking to learn the Chinese language, where he also examined different styles of Chinese fighting techniques there. He also published various books, including "Dynamic Karate," a top to bottom scientific method of Kihon, and several videos of specialized and pragmatic data on Kata, Kihon, and Kumite. Sensei Masatoshi Nakayama held the position of 10th Dan at the age of 74. When Master Nakayama died, the JKA suffered disturbances, continuing for two decades.

In **1986**, **Nobuyuki Nakahara** (Born on December 11, 1934), a recognized business tycoon and former Tokyo University Karate Club partner, was delegated as the 8th Chairman of the JKA. Japan Karate Association (JKA) is a top and reputed Karate organization at the international level. Masters who represent the JKA Shotokan Karate at a global scale, are **Taiji Kase** (February 9, 1929 – November 24, 2004) from the European branch in Paris, **Hideki Ochi** in Germany, **Hiroshi Shirai** in Italy, **Keinosuke Enoeda** (July 4, 1935 – March 29, 2003) in Great Britain, **Satoshi Miyazaki** (June 17, 1938 – May 31, 1993) in Belgium, **Higashino** in Brazil, **Ishiyama** in Venezuela, **Stan Schmidt** (the first non-Japanese fifth dan in South Africa, **Hideki Okamoto** (July 30, 1941– April 30, 2009) in Syria and Lebanon, **Masahiko Tanaka** (born on February 24, 1941) in Denmark, **Sasaki** in the Philippines, **Hiroshi Matsuura** in Mexico, and others. Around 5,000,000 individuals currently rehearse the JKA Shotokan karate-do in almost every nation in the world. The command of the JKA is to add to world harmony by directing exploration and giving Karate-do guidance. It aims at affecting youngsters and teenagers to improve their physical and emotional well-being just as developing the soul of combative techniques and the idea of Japanese martial art which highlights behaviour and honour.

In **1990**, the official status of the JKA was in a crisis when a few of its segregated members unlawfully changed the executive register. It faced a massive disaster for a long time. The Japan Supreme Court rejected these separated members' appeal in **June 1999** and closed the case forever. During this period, the JKA continued its progress under the instructions of the Chief Instructor Master **Sugiura Motokuni** (October 4, 1924 – August 10, 2015). With its lawful status re-established by court decisions, the JKA jumped into the 21st Century. It re-built its interior association and revamped its monetary base. In **December 2000**, it bought land and set up its new central command and dojo in the centre of Tokyo. The fantastic opening function was held in **May 2001**, by various dignitaries and numerous individuals from other karate associations. With recharged power, the JKA repositioned itself, plainly characterizing itself as "**The Keeper of Karate's Highest Tradition.**" In **2004**, the JKA introduced an official website, through which it proceeds, as usual, to advance genuine Karate around the globe.